

Synthesis and plant growth retardant activity of bis-quaternary salts of ammonia from phenols

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Manuscript received 28 September 2004, revised 10 May 2005, accepted 17 August 2005

Trialkylamines 3-(2-benzylphenoxy)-1-*N,N*-diethylaminopropan-2-ol (4a), 3-(4-benzylphenoxy)-1-*N,N*-diethylaminopropan-2-ol (4b), 3-(5-*n*-butoxyphenoxy)-1-*N,N*-diethylaminopropan-2-ol (4c) and 4,4'-bis(3-*N,N*-diethylamin-2-hydroxypropanoxy)biphenyl (9) were prepared from respective phenols and converted into corresponding bis-quaternary salts by reacting (4a-c) with malonyl chloride and (9) with ethyl bromide. These salts were tested for biological activity on germination, seedling growth and adventitious root formation on hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata* (SML-668). The results of biological studies of different compounds show that these salts do not inhibit seed germination and rather promotory in increasing shoot elongation if used from 10–50 µg/ml. However, all those compounds showed inhibitory action at higher concentration i.e. 100 µg/ml.

Plant growth retardants have been used for many years to manipulate the size, shape and overall quality of floricultural crops. Quaternary salts of ammonia have been found to possess plant growth retardant activity. These compounds have been used to control the lodging, in increasing the yield and producing the compact plant in different crops. In continuation to our work on the synthesis and growth retarding activity of trialkyl, ammonium compounds^{2,3}, we have now studied four new bis-quaternary ammonium compounds having phenoxy moiety, as plant growth retardants.

Results and discussion

Different phenols (1a-c) were treated with epi-chlorohydrin using potassium hydroxide to give a mixture of 2a-c in which nucleophile attacked the carbon bearing chlorine and 3a-c in which this attack was on epoxy ring. This was checked by TLC (two spots) and authenticated by literature^{4,5}. The mixture as such was then treated with alcoholic solution of diethylamine³ to get hydroxy tert.-amines (4a-c). The PMR spectra depicts characteristic peaks at δ 1.2 (6H, t, *J* 7 Hz, N(CH₂CH₃)₂) and 2.42 (6H, m, CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂). The bis-quaternary salts (5a-c) were then prepared by refluxing the acid chloride 7 (prepared from malonic acid by reacting with thionyl chloride) and tertiary amines⁶ (4a-c).

4,4'-Bis(3-*N,N*-diethylamin-2-hydroxypropanoxy)biphenyl (9) was prepared by reacting 4,4'-dihydroxy-biphenyl with epichlorohydrin followed by the reaction on the mixture of two products (7, 8) (obtained in the above step as evidenced by its TLC and supported by literature^{4,5}) with diethylamine in absolute alcohol³. Its PMR spectrum depicts a triplet at δ 1.3 for twelve protons corresponding to 2-N(CH₂CH₃)₂ and a multiplet at δ 2.5 for twelve protons 2-CH₂N(CH₂CH₃)₂. The tertiary amine (9) was then refluxed with ethyl bromide in dry acetone⁷ to get bis-quaternary salt of ammonia (10) in quantitative yield.

In general, all the compounds (5a-c and 10) prepared are insoluble in apolar organic solvents and therefore stirred with dry ether to remove any unreacted tertiary amines (4a-c and 9) and alkyl halides and then preserved in vacuum desiccator. They are hygroscopic in nature and their spectral studies could not be done.

Biological activity :

Germination of seeds in response to different concentrations of tested compounds remained almost comparable with control (100%). However, their effect was differential on the seedling growth measured in terms of length of shoot and root. The length of shoot increased in response to all the tested concentrations of various compounds as compared to control (Table 1). However, the magnitude of decrease declined with increasing concentrations of the compounds. The root length was increased in response to 10 and 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentrations of tested compounds as compared to control followed by decrease thereafter with maximum effect being exerted by 10 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration of compound **5a**.

Table 1 shows the effect of tested compounds on the initiation of rooting on hypocotyl cuttings of *Vigna radiata*. These compounds inhibited the number of roots initiated on the hypocotyl cuttings and their elongation growth.

The majority of plant growth retardants, the inhibitors of distinct steps of gibberallin biosynthesis are reported to exert broad range of effects on plant growth¹. However, the tested concentrations of quaternary ammonium salts on seed germination studies during present investigations are not found effecting in eliciting growth retardant activity. Further detailed studies using higher concentrations of the tested compounds are in progress in order to exploit their potential as growth retardants.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated all organic extract were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and purity of analytical samples was checked by TLC. PMR spectra (90 MHz) were recorded in CCl_4 in EM 360/390 NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts in δ , ppm). IR spectra (thin film) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 infrared spectrophotometer (ν_{max} in cm^{-1}).

1-N,N-Diethylamino-3-(2-benzylphenoxy)propan-2-ol (4a): 2-Benzylphenol (**1a**; 5 g, 0.027 mol) was dissolved in aqueous KOH (7%, 45 ml) and epichlorohydrin (10 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring at 10–15°. The stirring was continued for 36 h at room temperature. The separated oil was extracted with benzene, washed with 10% NaOH and finally with water. Removal of the benzene from the dried extract followed by distillations under reduced pressure of residual oil afforded a thick material. Its TLC showed two spots.

The above mixture (4.6 g) and diethylamine (5 ml) was

refluxed in absolute alcohol (50 ml) for 4 h, cooled and alcohol was distilled under reduced pressure to give **4a**, yield, 4.6 g (57%), b.p. 110–112°/5–10 mm; ν_{max} 3379, 3064, 1633, 1494, 1037, 785 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.2 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.2 (2H, s, benzylproton), 2.52 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.7 (2H, s, Ar- CH_2), 3.9 (3H, m, $\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})$), 7.2–7.4 (9H, m, Ar-H).

The compounds **4b,c** and **9** were prepared similarly from 4-benzyl phenol (**1b**), 5-butoxy-1-naphthol (**1c**) and 4,4'-biphenyl (**6**) respectively: **4b**, yield (67%), b.p. 105–108°/7–8 mm; ν_{max} 3340, 1650, 1158, 1006 and 786 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.10 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.44 (6H, m, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.75 (2H, s, Ar- CH_2), 3.81 (3H, m, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{CHCOH}$), 7.3–7.5 (9H, m, Ar-H); **4c**, yield (44%), b.p. 115–118°/10–12 mm; ν_{max} 3410, 3065, 1618, 1087, 906 and 780 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.95 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $-\text{CH}_3$), 1.2 (6H, t, J 7 Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 1.4 (4H, m, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 3.9 (5H, m, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})$, Ar- OCH_2), 7.5–8.0 (6H, m, Ar-H); **9**, yield (50%), b.p. 120–125°/10–12 mm; ν_{max} 3406, 3036, 1615, 1000 and 786 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.2 (12H, t, J 7 Hz, 2- $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.5 (12H, m, 2- $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.9 (6H, m, 2- $\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}(\text{OH})$), 5.2 (2H, 2-OH), 7.0–7.4 (8H, m, Ar-H).

Quaternary salts (5a-c). General procedure: A solution of freshly distilled malonyl chloride (0.85 g, 0.006 mol) in chloroform (10 ml) was added dropwise to tertiary amines **4a-c** (0.01 mol) dissolved in chloroform (40 ml) under anhydrous conditions at 0–5° with continues stirring. After the addition was over, the mixture was stirred for 3 h at same temperature and then at room temperature for 1 h. Distillation of chloroform followed by scratching, the residue with anhydrous ether afforded the bis-quaternary salts (**5a-c**) as thick oils, yields 80–86% and stored in vacuum desiccator. The spectral studies of these salts could not be done because of the hygroscopic nature of these salts. However, these salts gave positive copper wire test.

Quaternary salt (10): A mixture of tertiary amine **9** (1.7 g, 0.004 mol), dissolved in dry acetone (30 ml) and ethylbromide (1.1 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h. Removal of acetone followed by scratching the residue with anhydrous ether afforded the quat. salt (**10**) as a thick oil, 2.2 g (87%). The spectral studies of the salt could not be done because of hygroscopic nature of the compound. However, the salt gave positive copper wire test.

Biological evaluation :

The biological activity of bis-quaternary salts of ammonia (**5a-c** and **10**) were tested on moong bean seeds (*Vigna radiata*, SML-668) using seed germination and rooting of

Table 1.

Compd. ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Growth retarding activity of various bis-quaternary salts of ammonia on rooting of hypocotyl cuttings and on seedling				Effect of different conc. of bis-quaternary ammonia salts on seedling growth of <i>Vigna radiata</i> (SML-668)			
	No. of roots (length of roots in cm)				Seedlings length RL ^a (SL ^a) in cm			
	5	10	15	20	10	25	50	100
5a	4.75 ± 0.5 (3.5 ± 1.2)	3.33 ± 1.1 (3.6 ± 1.03)	3.0 ± 0.0 (4.0 ± 1.0)	3.0 ± 0.0 (3.7 ± 0.5)	10.13 ± 0.4 (5.08 ± 0.4)	7.45 ± 1.5 (5.6 ± 0.4)	7.3 ± 0.5 (2.8 ± 0.76)	7.2 ± 0.4 (2.1 ± 0.5)
5b	5.0 ± 0.0 (3.0 ± 0.0)	4.2 ± 0.0 (2.0 ± 0.0)	4.0 ± 0.0 (3.0 ± 0.0)	3.5 ± 0.5 (3.0 ± 0.2)	11.3 ± 1.4 (4.2 ± 0.4)	10.6 ± 1.1 (3.7 ± 0.9)	10.2 ± 1.8 (2.6 ± 0.9)	6.05 ± 1.7 (2.6 ± 0.6)
5c	4.2 ± 0.1 (3.1 ± 0.1)	4.0 ± 0.0 (3.2 ± 0.0)	3.8 ± 0.5 (3.0 ± 0.0)	3.5 ± 0.5 (3.0 ± 0.2)	8.2 ± 0.5 (4.2 ± 0.3)	6.5 ± 0.4 (4.0 ± 0.3)	6.4 ± 0.5 (3.6 ± 0.5)	5.3 ± 0.3 (3.5 ± 0.1)
10	5.0 ± 0.0 (3.0 ± 0.0)	4.0 ± 1.0 (3.6 ± 0.8)	3.6 ± 0.8 (3.5 ± 0.7)	3.5 ± 0.7 (3.5 ± 0.7)	10.0 ± 0.5 (4.9 ± 0.6)	10.0 ± 1.2 (4.6 ± 0.6)	10.0 ± 1.0 (4.3 ± 1.4)	9.6 ± 1.0 (3.9 ± 0.7)
Water (control)	5.0 ± 0.06 (4.0 ± 1.2)				4.6 ± 1.2 (3.9 ± 0.8)			

^aRL. Root length; SL. Shoot length.

hypocotyl assays. For germination studies seeds were surface sterilized with 0.1% mercuric chloride and germinated in Petridishes lined with double layer of filter paper to which 7 ml of test solution of different concentrations of the compounds were added. Data on percent germination and seedling length was collected after 48 h and 7 days of incubation at 28 ± 2°C respectively.

To test the activity of salts on rooting, 10 cuttings of hypocotyl of mungbean were taken in a vial containing (5, 10, 15 and 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of various compounds and incubated at 28 ± 2° for 7 days and thereafter number of roots initiated were recorded. For control, hypocotyl cuttings were incubated in distilled water.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. (Mrs.) N. Setia, Senior Plant Physiologist-cum-Head, Department of Botany, Pun-

jab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, for helping in the study of biological activity.

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